

Polarographic Behaviour of Some Azo Compounds

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Polarographic reduction mechanism of azo compounds in various buffers with pH ranging between 2 and 12 and at constant temperature of 25° was studied. In most cases, two $E_{1/2}$ - pH relationships were evaluated. The diffusion controlled reduction behaviour was observed. In acid and alkaline ranges the products of reaction were not identical. The proposed reaction mechanism highlights the product formation with the electrons consumed.

DISPROPORTIONATION of azo compounds proceeded by acid and/or base catalysed mechanism, coupled with redox reaction between the hydrazo derivative and certain intermediate was suggested by Florence¹. The number of electrons involved in reduction of compounds are different and depend on pH as well as the substituents on the electrochemical active moiety. At higher pH, the possibility of slow reaction followed by the uptake of 2e is evident from the coulometric² value of $n \approx 3$. Malik and Gupta³ proposed a detailed mechanism (H^+ , e, e, H^+) accounting for the effect of substituents on $E_{1/2}$ of solochrome azo dyes, the final product being primarily hydrazo derivatives. Madajova and Zelensky⁴ reviewed the influence of structure of azo compounds and their pK values and concluded that neutral and protonated species behaved differently at the d.m.e. Abdel-Kader and El-Arab⁵ besides confirming some of well established facts, indicated the reduction of azo compounds is irreversible, a contrast with the observation of other workers⁶, who showed that reduction was partly reversible. The study of several hydroxy derivatives of azo compounds in the universal buffer indicated one wave in acid range and two waves⁷ in alkaline media, thereby indicating two distinct reduction mechanisms for the same compound.

The conclusions drawn earlier seem not wholly convincing as yet regarding the reduction mechanism because of the complex behaviour of azo group at the d.m.e.⁸⁻¹⁰. In the present communication, the investigations on the various azo compounds have been reported and it is attempted to establish the possible reasons for the different mechanisms of the reduction.

Experimental

Azo compounds were prepared by the diazotization method with $NaNO_2$ in HCl media, followed by alkaline coupling, and purified by recrystallisation from 50% spectroscopic alcohol and dried over BaO in vacuum desiccator. Purity as determined by potentiometry was found to range between 99.2 to

99.3% for different compounds. Azo benzene (B.D.H., A.R.) was used without purification. The following standard buffer¹¹ solutions were prepared and used. (i) Prideaux and Ward (H_3PO_4 , phenylacetic acid, H_3BO_3 and NaOH), pH 2.0-11.9, (ii) Britton-Robinson (H_3PO_4 , CH_3COOH , H_3BO_3 and NaOH), pH 2.0-12.0, (iii) Britton-Robinson (HCl, KH_2PO_4 , citric acid, H_3BO_3 , veronal and NaOH), pH 2.5-12.0, (iv) Britton-Robinson (KH_2PO_4 , citric acid, H_3BO_3 , veronal and NaOH), pH 3.8-12.0, (v) German and Vogel (phenylacetic acid and sodium phenyl acetate), pH 3.5-5.2, (vi) McIlvaine (Na_2HPO_4 and citric acid), pH 2.2-8.0, (vii) Clark and Lubs (KH_2PO_4 and NaOH), pH 5.8-8.0, (viii) Kolthoff (KH_2PO_4 and borax), pH 5.8-9.2, (ix) Clark and Lubs (H_3BO_3 and NaOH), pH 7.8-10.0 and (x) Sorensen (borax and HCl), pH 7.6-9.3.

Apparatus :

Measurements were made with the dropping mercury electrode in a Novak type cell in conjunction with universal pen recording polarograph (model OH-105, Hungary). The polarographic cell was maintained at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ by ultrathermostat (G.D.R.). The capillary characteristics were 1.805 $mg^{2/3}s^{-1/2}$ at 52 cm when short circuited (vs S.C.E.). All potentials are reported against saturated calomel electrode.

Procedure : Several concentrations of each compound were maintained with buffer solutions and $NaNO_2$ ($\mu=1$). The solutions were deaerated by bubbling purified N_2 before subjecting to record polarograms. No maximum suppressor was used.

Results and Discussion

No appreciable effect of buffer constituents and their pH value on the limiting current was noted. The waves seem to be diffusion-controlled from the plots of i vs \sqrt{h} ; i vs C and low temperature coefficient (1.27 to 3.2% K^{-1}). The waves, in general, were well formed; deformed mostly in German and Vogel as well as in Prideaux and Ward buffers for azobenzene and its derivatives but well defined

TABLE 1— $E_{1/2}$ - pH RELATIONSHIP OF AZO COMPOUNDS AND SUBSTITUENT EFFECTS

Sl no.	Compd. (medium)	Substituent	$E_{1/2}$ - pH equation (pH range)	At pH 4.8		$\Delta E_{1/2}/V$	ρ	$\Sigma\sigma$
				$-E_{1/2}/V$ vs S.O.E.	$-E^0/V$			
1.	Azobenzene (H ₂ O)	none	$E_{1/2} = 0.06 - 0.06 \text{ pH}$ (2.0-7.5) $E_{1/2} = 0.09 - 0.05 \text{ pH}$ (7.5-12)	0.228	0.220	—	—	—
2.	4-Hydroxyazobenzene (H ₂ O)	4(OH)	$E_{1/2} = 0.08 - 0.070 \text{ pH}$ (2-7) $E_{1/2} = 0.085 - 0.075 \text{ pH}$ (7-12)	0.280	0.252	-0.052	0.14	-0.37
3.	4-Sulphonic acid azobenzene (H ₂ O)	4(SO ₃ H)	$E_{1/2} = 0.12 - 0.06 \text{ pH}$ (2-8) $E_{1/2} = 0.14 - 0.05 \text{ pH}$ (8-12)	0.168	0.132	0.06	0.14	0.43
4.	4-Nitroazobenzene (0% CH ₃ OH)	4(NO ₂)	$E_{1/2} = 0.25 - 0.06 \text{ pH}$ (2-8) $E_{1/2} = 0.30 - 0.05 \text{ pH}$ (8-12)	0.038	0.032	0.19	0.14	1.36
5.	4,4'-Disulphonic acid azobenzene (H ₂ O)	4(SO ₃ H) 4'(SO ₃ H)	$E_{1/2} = 0.16 - 0.06 \text{ pH}$ (2-7)	0.128	0.11	0.10	0.14	0.71
6.	4,4'-Dihydroxyazobenzene (H ₂ O)	4(OH) 4'(OH)	$E_{1/2} = 0.11 - 0.12 \text{ pH}$ (2-7)	0.466	0.435	-0.238	0.14	-1.7
7.	1-(2-Hydroxyphenylazo)-2-naphthol (H ₂ O)	none	$E_{1/2} = 0.03 - 0.065 \text{ pH}$ (2-7.5) $E_{1/2} = 0.035 - 0.06 \text{ pH}$ (7.5-12)	0.342	0.252	—	—	—
8.	1-(4-Hydroxynaphthylazo)benzene-4-sulphonic acid (H ₂ O)	4(SO ₃ H)	$E_{1/2} = 0.125 - 0.09 \text{ pH}$ (2-6.0) $E_{1/2} = 0.10 - 0.06 \text{ pH}$ (7-12)	0.307	0.216	0.035	0.16	0.22
9.	1-(2-Hydroxynaphthylazo)-2-phenol sulphonic acid (H ₂ O)	4(SO ₃ H) 2(OH)	$E_{1/2} = 0.02 - 0.06 \text{ pH}$ (2-7) $E_{1/2} = 0.04 - 0.05 \text{ pH}$ (8-12)	0.308	0.215	-0.034	0.16	0.21
10.	4-Hydroxy-3-(2-hydroxynaphthylazo)-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid (H ₂ O) (Eriochrome violet B)	4(SO ₃ H) 4(OH)	$E_{1/2} = 0.02 - 0.06 \text{ pH}$ (2-7) $E_{1/2} = -0.035 - 0.055 \text{ pH}$ (7-12)	0.308	0.208	0.034	0.16	0.21
11.	1-(2-Hydroxynaphthylazo)-2-naphthol (H ₂ O)	none	$E_{1/2} = 0.085 - 0.08 \text{ pH}$ (2-8)	0.30	0.15	—	—	—
12.	1-(2-Hydroxynaphthylazo)-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid (H ₂ O)	4(SO ₃ H)	$E_{1/2} = 0.02 - 0.06 \text{ pH}$ (2-7) $E_{1/2} = 0.026 - 0.05 \text{ pH}$ (7-12)	0.268	0.132	+0.032	0.18	0.178
13.	1-(2-Hydroxynaphthylazo)-2-naphthol-7-nitro-4-sulphonic acid (H ₂ O) (Solochrome black AS)	4(SO ₃ H) 7(NO ₂)	$E_{1/2} = -0.028 - 0.06 \text{ pH}$ (2-6) $E_{1/2} = -0.04 - 0.05 \text{ pH}$ (7-12)	0.316	0.168	-0.016	0.18	-0.088

in Britton-Robinson (pH 2.0-12.0), McIlvaine and Clark and Lubs (pH 7.8-10.0). Solochrome black AS gave ill-defined wave in basic medium in most of the buffers, while Eriochrome violet B resulted in ill-defined wave in acidic medium in all the universal buffers studied.

The dyes^{1,2} get aggregated in the presence of foreign ions and more particularly at high concentration, which has been observed even at a concentration 0.1 mM. The concentration range of the compounds is selected in a precise manner to deprive them of this property. Invariably appreciably low concentrations were chosen to ensure the measurements in monomeric form rather than in the aggregated one.

The shift in $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential with pH with a break at higher pH values, in general, was noted, an observation in confirmation with earlier work. Therefore, two ($E_{1/2}$ - pH) equations have been proposed depending on whether pH range is low or high. Disubstituted sulphonic acid and hydroxyazobenzenes (compounds 3 and 6) and dinaphthyl derivatives (compound 11) showed no break in the entire range of pH values in which study was possible (Table 1). Beyond pH 8.0,

certain difficulties were encountered which adversely affect the results with the exclusively symmetrical molecules. In case of azobenzene (which apparently is most symmetrical of all), no such problem was encountered, may be due to the predominating *trans* form which is known for distinct behaviour at the d.m.e. in the acidic and basic media⁸.

$\Sigma\sigma$ values reported in Table 1 resemble favourably with the values reported by Florence¹⁰ on the similar type of compounds.

The conventional log plots reveal irreversible reduction of these compounds at the d.m.e. An alternate approach through the comparison of $E_{1/2}$ with E^0 (apparent redox potential) was applied to decide about the reversibility. E^0 determined by potential mediator method at pH 4.8 compares fairly closely with $E_{1/2}$ (Table 1) for azobenzene and its derivatives, while the differences are moderate to high for other two classes of compounds. Thus it can be concluded that the reduction was not reversible invariably, *i.e.* the molecular size have had its effect on the reversible reduction process.

Electrode mechanism: The reduction is primarily acid catalysed at low and high pH values. At high

pH values a part of the reduction is in homogeneous solution. Consequently, the following different pathways are possible :

- (i) The 2e wave of azo compound at pH < 7 appears at less negative potential and is pH-independent. In acid media, the uptake of 2H⁺, 2e followed by fast proton attack is the major step. This protonated hydrazo derivative may undergo cleavage of N-N to form diimine derivative which is reduced to 2,4-dihydroxy aniline (3) derivative by further consuming 2H⁺ and 2e, thereby totalling 4e for the entire process.
- (ii) At pH > 7 < 12, the height of the wave is less than that observed in acidic medium^{5,6}, the E_{1/2} shifted towards negative value. The first step seems to be 2H⁺, 2e resulting in the formation of hydrazo derivative, followed by a fast base (OH⁻) attack and simultaneously undergoing hydrolysis to produce diimine. The diimine eventually prefer the homogeneous reaction with the hydrazo intermediate to regenerate azo compound for further electro-reduction and formation of aniline derivatives (3). Hence, only one 2e wave would be possible at pH value where reaction is fast enough to transfer hydrazo derivative to products and azo compounds.

The first step in this Scheme is simultaneous protonation and electron transfer process. This is followed by a slow single electron attack to form radical anion¹³ depending upon the substituents in two moieties to undergo two possible mode of reaction, i.e. homogeneous reaction to dimerise^{13,14} and/or addition of further electron and proton to give aniline derivatives. It is evident from Table 2 in which proposed products of electrode reactions *vis-a-vis* electron consumption of 2,2',4-trihydroxyazobenzene are shown, that in acidic media the

TABLE 2—PROPOSED REACTION PRODUCTS OF 2,2',4-TRIHYDROXYAZOBENZENE (1)

Number of electrons involved \bar{n}	pH < 7	pH > 7
2	2,2',4 Trihydroxyhydrazo-benzene (2) + diimine derivative not favourable to homogeneous reaction	2,2',4-Trihydroxyhydrazo-benzene (2) + diimine derivative favour the homogeneous reaction to regenerate (1) and 3,4-dihydroxy aniline (3)
3	—	Radical anion dimerisation to give 2,2',4,4'-tetrahydroxyhydrazobenzene (4) and 2-hydroxy aniline (5)
4	2,4-Dihydroxyaniline (3) and 2-hydroxyaniline (5)	2,4-Dihydroxy-aniline (6)

An alternate sequence to determine the relative rates of protonation, electron transfer and radical dimerization can be proposed for azo compounds in alkaline media.

products are different from that in alkaline media. In no case, the set of the product(s) was similar. Exactly same behaviour was noted with all other compounds under discussion. This envisages that

the reaction of azo group follows a complicated mechanism at the d.m.e., which besides depending upon the substituents *etc.* would depend also on pH values of the buffer.

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